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PHARMACOGNOSTICAL AND PHYSICOCHEMICAL STANDARDISATION OF *CHANDANADI AGADA*- A POLYHERBAL AGADA PREPARATION

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Abstract

Evaluating the quality control of poly-herbal formulations is very important to validate their suitability within the contemporary healthcare system, even if the medication holds therapeutic potential. The growing popularity of Ayurveda among the public has introduced numerous new challenges and concerns. The standardization of the drugs is very essential for achieving the intended impact of the formulation and to maintain the standard limits of a formulation. Here an attempt is made to develop standard limits of the anti-poisonous polyherbal formulation *Chandanadi Agada*. **Materials and methods:** After the authentication of raw drugs, *Chandanadi Agada* was prepared as per classical reference and the organoleptic, powder microscopy and physicochemical standards of the formulations were carried out. **Results and Discussion:** The pH 6.5 of *Chandanadi Agada* suggested the drug is slightly acidic. The Loss on drying at 110°C was 3.45%, Total ash value was 7.32%, Water soluble extractive was 34.14% and Alcohol soluble extractive (ASE) value was 38.2%. **Conclusion:** The raw drugs were found to be genuine in pharmacognostical evaluation. The organoleptic and physicochemical parameters can be used as reference standards for the quality control.

Key Words:

Chandanadi Agada, Pharmacognostical parameter, Physicochemical parameter, Standardization

INTRODUCTION:

In pharmaceutical study, the main aim is to develop a standard procedure for the preparation of *Chandanadi Agada*. Ayurveda medicines comprise herbal, herbo-mineral and mineral preparations. The SMP varies with various *Kalpanas* Standardization of Ayurvedic medications is crucial to avoiding drug adulteration, achieving the intended impact of the medication, and eliminating unwholesome side effects. In order to address this, a comprehensive study was conducted to evaluate the quality of the raw materials and finished products. The results were compared with criteria set by the Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India (API), the Indian Herbal Pharmacopoeia, and the ICMR's guidelines on 'Quality Standards of Indian Medicinal Plants.

Chandanadi Agada is a potential polyherbal anti poisonous formulation containing four drugs; *Chandana*, *Neeli*, *Kushtha* and *Tanduleeyaka*.¹

Materials and Methods:**MATERIALS**

	Name of drug	Latin name	Family	Part used	Proportion
1.	<i>Sweta Chandana</i>	<i>Santalum album</i> Linn.	Santalaceae	Heartwood	1 part
2.	<i>Neeli</i>	<i>Indigofera tinctoria</i> Linn	Fabaceae/ Leguminosae	Root	1 part
3.	<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Saussurea lappa</i> C.B. Clarke	Asteraceae	Root	1 part
4.	<i>Tanduleeyaka</i>	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> Linn.	Amaranthaceae	Root	1 part
5.	<i>Godugdha</i>	-	-	-	Quantity sufficient

METHODOLOGY:**Procurement of raw materials:**

Chandana (*Santalum album* Linn.) and *Kushtha* (*Saussurea lappa* C.B. Clarke) were procured from the Pharmacy, ITRA, Jamnagar. *Neeli* (*Indigofera tinctoria* Linn) and *Tanduleeyaka* (*Amaranthus spinosus* Linn.) were purchased from other authentic sources due to the non-availability of drugs in Pharmacy, ITRA, Jamnagar. After collection of herbal raw materials, authentication was done by experts of Pharmacognosy Laboratory of ITRA, Jamnagar. Cow milk for the preparation of drug was procured from a local cow husbandry, Jamnagar.

Preparation of Chandanadi Agada

All the authenticated drugs were powdered separately, passed through 72 no. sieve and then mixed together in specified proportions (Table 1) to get uniformly blended *Churna*. *Bhavana* was given in *Godugdha*. The powder was again filtered through 120 no. sieve and fine powder obtained was stored in airtight container.

Table 1– Ingredients of Chandanadi Agada

	Drug name	Parts used	Proportion
1	<i>Sweta Chandana</i>	Heart wood	1 part
2	<i>Neeli</i>	Root	1 part
3	<i>Kushta</i>	Root	1 part
4	<i>Tanduleeyaka</i>	Root	1 part
5	<i>Godugdha</i>	-	Quantity sufficient

Pharmacognostic Evaluation:

- Macroscopic characteristics of raw materials
- Microscopic evaluation

Table 2: Macroscopic characteristics of raw materials

Sr No	Sample	Parameters			
		<i>Rupa</i> (Colour)	<i>Gandha</i> (Odour)	<i>Rasa</i> (Taste)	<i>Sparsha</i> (Touch)
1.	<i>Shweta Chandana</i>	Brown	Aromatic	Bitter	Smooth
2.	<i>Neeli</i>	Creamish brown	Not specific	Bitter	Smooth
3.	<i>Kushtha</i>	Dark brown	Pungent	Bitter	Smooth
4.	<i>Tanduliyaka</i>	Pale brown	Not specific	Bitterish	Fibrous

The macroscopic characters of the drugs were observed as per API. Chandana² was hard heavy with smooth transverse surface and showed alternate light and dark concentric zones. Neeli³ roots were hard and woody pieces with thick surface. The colour observed was pale yellow to light yellow. Kushtha⁴ roots were dull brown colour and inner surface was light in colour. Tanduleeyaka roots were easily breakable with light colour. Surface was smooth.

Microscopic Characters Identified;

Fig - 1 (a)

Fig -1 (b)

Fig -1 (c)

Fig -1 (d)

Fig -1 (e)

Fig -1 (f)

Fig -1 (g)

Fig -1 (h)

Fig -1 (i)

Fig - 1 (a): Stone cells of *Chandana*, Fig -1 (b): Lignified fibre with oil globule of *Chandana*, Fig -1 (c): Fibres of *Chandana*, Fig -1 (d): Spiral vessels of *Neeli*, Fig -1 (e): Epidermal cells of *Neeli*, Fig -1 (f): Fibres of *Kushtha*, Fig -1 (g): Oil globule of *Kushtha*, Fig -1 (h): Crystal of *Tanduliyaka*, Fig -1 (i): Starch grains of *Tanduliyaka*

Organoleptic parameters of the finished drug

Colour, Touch, Odour and Taste of the finished drug were assessed.

Physico chemical evaluation

The Physicochemical Analysis of *Chandanadi Agada* was carried out as per the standard protocol mentioned in the Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India. pH value⁵, Loss on drying⁶, total ash value⁷, Water-soluble extractive value⁸, Alcohol-soluble extractive value⁹ were assessed.

Source

Macroscopic and microscopic evaluation of raw drugs and finished drug were analysed in Pharmacognosy laboratory ITRA, Jamnagar. Organoleptic and physico-chemical studies were conducted in Pharmaceutical Chemistry Laboratory, ITRA, Jamnagar.

Results**Table 3: Organoleptic Parameters of finished drug**

Sr. No	Powder Organoleptic Characters	
1	Colour	Dark brown
2	Odour	Characteristic
3	Taste	Bitter astringent
4	Nature of the powder	Smooth

Physico-chemical Parameters of Chandanadi Agada**Table 4: Physico-Chemical Analysis**

No	Parameters	Value
1	Loss on drying	3.45%
2	Ash value	7.32%
3	Water soluble extractive value	34.14%
4	Alcohol soluble extractive value	38.2%
5	pH value	6.5

Discussion

Pharmacognosy studies: All the drugs were confirmed to be genuine, free from adulteration or substitution, thus proved suitable and safe for medical use. Microscopic characteristics of *Chandanadi Agada* are suggestive of authenticity of raw drugs.

Physico-chemical Parameters:

The pH 6.5 suggest that the drug is slightly acidic in nature.

The amount of inorganic residue that remains after oxidizing or incinerating organic matter is known as the ash value or ash content. As an essential qualitative standard, ash value helps establish the authenticity and purity of a sample. The inorganic substances in the sample were found to be within normal limits, according to the determined ash value of 7.32 percent.

The lower LOD value measures the amount of moisture or volatile matter in a sample. LOD can help determine a product's stability, longevity, and processing characteristics. LOD value of *Chandanadi Agada* is found as 3.45% which indicates that the stability of the drug is good.

Water-soluble and alcohol-soluble extractives can assess the quality and purity of a drug. A medicine's water-soluble extractive value measures the amount of water-soluble components it contains. A decrease in extractive value could be due to the addition of exhausted materials, adulteration, improper drying, storage, or formulation processes. The drug's high WSE value of 34.14% indicates its purity.¹⁰ The alcohol-soluble extractive value measures the amount of polar components in plant material that are soluble in alcohol.¹¹ A large percentage of the phytochemical components of *Chandanadi Agada* are soluble in alcohol media, according to its high ASE value of 38.2%. It is found that *Chandanadi Agada* has a higher water-soluble extractive value compared to its alcohol-soluble extractive value.

Conclusion

Present work carried out for development of quality standards of *Chandanadi Agada*. Organoleptic and Physicochemical studies, have been useful for identity of the formulation. The results obtained from this study could be utilised for the standardization of formulations.

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Conflict of interest: Nil

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